

Edible Insects as an Alternative Source of Nutritional Consumption

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ABSTRACTS

The increasing in global population, coupled with pressure on traditional livestock systems, has necessitated the search of alternative and sustainable sources of nutrition. Edible insects have surface as a promising solution due to their high nutritional value, low environmental impact, and cultural acceptance in many countries particularly in Nigeria. This study investigates the potential of the Field crickets and Winged termites as an alternative source of nutritional consumption, the nutritional quality of protein, fat, minerals, vitamins were determined using standard methods. The active substances from these two edible insects in the Southern Nigeria have a variety of bio functional values, the essentials and non – essentials amino-acids and anti-nutrients analysis were determined. Edible insects are highly nutritious and it can be served as good source of nutrient, vitamins minerals that may be useful in combating related disease, and can be consumed as alternative to other source of protein.

Keywords: *Field Crickets, Winged termites, proximate analysis, nutrients.*

INTRODUCTION

Insect is the most varied clusters of multicellular organisms accounting for over 70% of all living species on earth (Raheem et al., 2019). Insect are known to be the largest group of the *Phylum Arthropoda* (Giribet and Edgecombe, 2019). The insect (class insecta) is the most living organism abundant in the world, the number of living insect species, are known to be in the range of 2.5 – 10 million (Eggleton, 2020).

In current years, the use of edible insect as a sustainable source of nutrient, has shown some degree of progress due to increased consumer acceptance and regulatory advance by some countries (Devi et al., 2024) due to these, thousands of insect species are consumed by a sizeable percentage of the human population around the world (Omuse et al., 2024).

Edible insects contain important nutrient, including protein, fatty acids and essential micronutrients (minerals and vitamin) which compares favourable to nutrients obtained from plants and animals (Oliveira et al., 2024).

World widely, over 2100 edible insects have been identify in various region of Asia, Africa and South America (Kipkoech et al., 2023). Edible insects are consumed in many African countries like DR. Congo, Cameron and Zambia lead in its consumption. About 22 insect species that include moths, grasshopper, cricket, termites are consumed in Nigeria (Raheem et al., 2019).

Anagonou et al., (2023) showed that edible insect including crickets, grasshoppers and termites form a significant part of the diet particularly in the Republic of Benin. These insects are typically consumed as snacks many times roasted or fried and sometime incorporated into sauces with staple food like maize and cassava (Anagonou et al., 2023).

Edible insects can be used as a sustainable alternative food and feed sources, particularly when compared to fish and meat. These could attribute to their low breeding space requirement and high feed conversion efficiency and even high rate of reproduction (Rumpold and Schluter 2013b). According to Raheem *et al.* (2019), edible insects are high in protein and contain higher protein than most other protein sources from plants and animals.

In Nigeria the rapid growth in population depends mainly on a small proportion of vertebrate protein and this is inadequate in production. Therefore, the use of insects and other plant materials were used by populace as an alternative to malnutrition, a situation whereby the children are most vulnerable.

Edible insect has gained great relevance as a food source in recent years, and this achievement is attributed to its high nutrients and value. According to Banjo (2006). About 200 species of insect out of the more than one million species occurring in nature are edible and can be food and serve as feed options, the major insects, consumed worldwide are beetles and caterpillars (49%) wasps and Ant (14%) locust and cricket (13%) hemipterans (10%) dragon flies (3%), in Southwest Nigeria some edible insects are recognized as food and source of nutrient.

The objectives of this study is to determine some of nutrient composition of the two commonly eaten insects in southwest of Nigeria

MATERIALS AND METHOD

SAMPLE COLLECTION AND PROCESSING

Winged termites (*Macrotermes bellicious*) were collected in the night after the rainfall and field cricket (*Gryllus Testaceus walker*) were collected in the farm during raining season between month of July and September. They were collected, washed and dewinged. The collected samples were roasted for ten minutes over a gas cooker and stored in a dried glass jar stored 4⁰C till when needed for analysis before grinding into powder (Igwe et al., 2011).

MOISTURE CONTENT

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Moisture content was determined by loss in weight on drying at 95.100°C for 8hrs in Gallenkamp UK", hot box even (AOAC 1999).

CRUDE PROTEIN CONTENT

Total protein was quantified by determining total nitrogen using Kjeldahl method. A conversion factor of 6.25 was used (AOAC 1999). 0.2g of samples was suspended in 15ml of pepsin buffer solution in a conical flask and incubated for 3hrs then shaken gently after every 20munutes. Digested samples were centrifuge at a force of 4025g for 15minutes and the supernant discarded. The residue was digested, centrifuged as before and filtered. The final residue was rolled up in the filter paper, place into a kjeldahl flask and dried in the oven at 100°C for 15minutes. About kjeldhl catalyst was added to the sample residues followed by heat digestion.

CRUDE FAT

Crude fat was quantified according to AOAC (1999) method. Extraction of fat was done on a soxhhlet extracting machine (HT 1043 extraction unit) using petroleum ether 40 – 60 boiling points as the extractant.

FIBRE

Dietary fibre was determined using the method of Saura-Calixto et al., 1983.

ASH CONTENT

The ash content was determined according to AOAC 1999. 2g of sample was weighed into a dry pre-weighed porcelain dish, transferred into the Cabioletfurance CNF 13/5 and the content was completely oxidized at 550°C for 8hrs. The ash content the reported as the loss in weight.

CARBOHYDRATES

The carbohydrates were determined by differences using standard equation $100\% - (\% \text{protein} - \% \text{fat} + \% \text{moisture})$.

ANALYSIS OF MINERALS

Samples were analyzed for major minerals like: Iron, Magnesium, Potassium, Phosphorus, Nickel, Manganese, Sodium, Calcium and Selenium using Perkin Elmer 23080 Atomic Absorption spectroscopy (AAS) following met digestion (Okalebo et al., 2002).

AMINO ACID DETERMINATION

Before analysis, samples were acid hydrolyzed with hydrochloric acid (6mol/L) at 110°C for 22hrs in glass tubes under nitrogen, performic acid was removed in a vacuum and the samples were hydrolyzed under a vacuum, dissolved in sodium citrate, pH, 2.2, and filter through a milipore membrane filter 0.45mm amino analyzer (model: 12IMP, Beckman Industries, Pale Alto, CA, USA) (Dun et al., 2004).

ANTI - NUTRIENT ANALYSIS

Phyate was determined by titration with ferric chloride solution (Sundamardj and Markakis, 1977). The tannin content was determined by extracting the samples with a mixture of acetone and acetic acid for 5hrs, measuring their absorbance and comparing the absorbance of standard solutions of tannic acid at 500nm on spectornic 20 (Griffiths and Tones 1977)

RESULTS

The nutritional composition of these two edible insects (Winged termites and Field Cricket) is summarized in Table 1). The winged termites were enriched in crude fat ($39.06 \pm 0.080\%$) protein ($37.08 \pm 0.080\%$) Moisture ($9.72 \pm 0.020\%$). The ash, fibre and carbohydrates contents were $7.01 \pm 0.040\%$, $6.18 \pm 0.01\%$ and $0.95 \pm 0.00\%$ respectively while the field cricket contains relatively high content of fat ($42.40 \pm 0.080\%$) protein ($35.12 \pm 0.082\%$) and moisture ($11.91 \pm 0.050\%$). And the fibre, ash and carbohydrates were 6.08 ± 0.040 , $3.98 \pm 0.050\%$ and 0.51 ± 0.040 respectively. The total amino acid composition for winged termites phenylalanine (51.11) tyrosine (48.66), Leucine (16.42) Threonine (12.68) Histidine (12.40), Lysine (6.66), Valine (3.62), methionine (1.46) and cysteine (0.58) while field cricket is phenylalanine (44.11) tyrosine (41.21), Leucine (19.66) threonine (14.67), Lysine (12.10), Histidine (10.10), valine (4.02) methionine (1.62) and cysteine (0.39) respectively. Phenylalanine, tyrosine and leucine and the most common essential amino acid, followed by threonine, histidine and lysine respectively.

The mineral composition in winged termites, the sample was high in potassium (3270.00mg/kg), Magnesium (43.91mg/kg), Sodium (11.10mg/kg), Iron (10.50mg/kg) and phosphorus (6.62mg/kg) with low content of calcium (1.00mg/kg), Nickel (0.70mg/kg) selenium (0.04mg/kg) and Manganese (0.30mg/kg). In field cricket potassium (446.89 mg/kg), magnesium (59.03mg/kg), sodium (15.10mg/kg), Nickel (5.30mg/kg) respectively.

The anti-nutrient composition of winged termites phytate (0.014g/100g) and tannin (1.138g/100g). the field cricket is 3.106/100g of tannin and 0.021/100g of phytate.

The two edible insect vitamin content is vitamin A. (0.38) (0.36), vitamin B, (1.55) (1.37), vitamin B₂ (0.67) (0.70), vitamin C (19.81), (17.11) and niacin (2.81) (6.97) respectively.

Table 1: Proximate Composition of Roasted Winged Termites and Field Crickets.

Nutrients g/100g	Winged Termites <i>M. Bellicosus</i>	Field Cricket <i>G. Testaceus</i>
Fat (%)	39.06 ± 0.08	42.40 ± 0.080
Fibre (%)	6.18 ± 0.01	6.08 ± 0.040
Ash (%)	7.01 ± 0.04	3.98 ± 0.050
Protein (%)	37.08 ± 0.08	35.12 ± 0.082
Moisture (%)	9.72 ± 0.02	11.91 ± 0.050
Carbohydrates (%)	0.95 ± 0.00	0.51 ± 0.040
Iron	10.50	3.90
Magnesium	43.91	59.03
Potassium	3270.0	446.89
Phosphorus	6.62	5.30
Nickel	0.70	0.90
Manganes	0.30	0.49
Sodium	11.10	15.10
Calcium	1.00	0.92
Selenium	0.04	0.003
Essential amino acids		
Phenylalamine	15.11	44.11
Tyrosine	48.66	41.21
Leucine	16.42	19.66
Threonine	12.68	14.67
Histidine	12.50	10.10
Lysine	6.66	12.10
Valine	3.62	4.02
Methionine	1.46	1.62
Cysteine	0.58	0.39
Non-essential amino acids		
Tryptophan	31.11	40.11
Servine	31.08	28.42
Proline	29.66	39.86
Arginine	28.42	38.21
Asparagine	26.41	31.62

Glutamic acid	22.21	29.99
Alunine	21.62	32.14
Glycine	19.86	38.86
Anti – nutrient		
Tannin	1.138	3.106
Phytate	0.014	0.021
Vitamin		
Vitamin A	0.38	0.36
Vitamin B ₁ (Thiamine)	1.55	1.37
Vitamin B ₂ (riboflavin)	0.67	0.70
Vitamin C	19.81	17.11
Niacin	2.81	6.97

Source; - Fiel work

DISCUSSION

In Nigeria many tribes traditionally used insect as food and drug mostly as a supplement for protein where necessary. The rapid growth in population in Nigeria required proportionate increase in food production. However, it is difficult to meet up with the level of populace demand. The present study confirmed that edible insects like winged termite and field cricket are rich in nutritional and mineral requirements of the body. Due to the shortage of food particular animal protein, consumption of insects could contribute to the dietary protein quality replacing higher animal protein deficient in diets of rural dwellers in developing countries (Banjo et al., 2006).

Edible insects such as field cricket and winged termite are rich in nutrition and mineral requirements for growth, maintenance of body functions as well as protection against infections (Roth and Townsend 2003; Roifes et al., 2009).

Roasted field cricket and winged termite has a fair content of major minerals such as potassium, sodium, phosphorous, iron, calcium nickel and mangnase. Minerals are known to play

important metabolic physiologic roles in the living system (Igwe et al., 2011). Manganese and selenium prevent cardiomyopathy, immunologic dysfunction and bleeding disorder (Chaturvedi et al., 2004).

The magnesium helps in maintaining normal nerve and muscle functions also support healthy immune system and keep heartbeat steady. The phosphorus also need by body to build strong health bones also helps in growth and maintenance and repair of cells and tissues. Potassium helps the nerves to function and muscles to contracts also maintain salt and water balance, while the iron helps in oxygenate the blood, convert blood sugar to energy, boost immunity and support healthy skin, hair and nails.

The edible insect rich in vitamins which maintain blood vessels flexibility and improves circulation also helps in antioxidant and play important role of co-enzymes in several enzyme systems of the body (Igwe et al., 2011). Edible insects have been a major source of nutrients to millions of people globally, (Magara et al., 2021; Jose et al., 2022 and Van Itterbeeck et al., 2022).

Several studies highlight the presence of high iron and zinc content in edible insects (Verspoor et al., 2020).

Besides food, several bioactive compounds and industrial products including polyunsaturated and monounsaturated fatty acids peptides, enzymes, antioxidant, and antimicrobial compounds can be obtained from edible insects (Ojha et al., 2021; Babarinde et al., 2020).

CONCLUSION

Edible insects show a sustainable and nutritious food source that can play an important role in addressing global food security and necessary nutrient challenges. The potential benefit makes it a worldwide venture, with embracing entomophagy, an effective protein ingredient that could replace meat and fish protein in our diets, because of high nutritional content, health promoting qualities, high sustainability and customer acceptance as existing researches confirm the considerable nutritional and medicinal values of edible insects.

REFERENCES

Anagonou, C. M., Loko, L. E. Y., Dassou, A. G., Toffa, J., Djegbe, I., Saliou, M.

and Dansi, A. (2023). Entomophagy practices, use patterns, and factors influencing perception and consumption frequency of edible insects in the Republic of Benin. *J. Ethnobiol. Ethnomed.* 19 p. 54.

AOAC (1999). Official methods of analysis of the association of official analytical chemists, 15th ed. USA Association of Official analytical chemists, pp85.

Babarinde, S.A. Mvumi, B.M. Babarinde G.O. Manditserd, F.A.; Akande T.O; and Adepoju, A. A. (2020). Insects in food and feed systems in Sub-Saharan Africa: The Untapped potentials. *International Journal of Tropical Insect science*, 41: (3) 1 – 12.

Banjo A.D. Lawal, O.A. and Sengonuga, E. A. (2006). The nutritional value of fourteen species of edible insects in south western Nigeria. *Africa Journ. Of Biotech*; 5 (3) 298 – 301.

Chaturvedi, V.C. Shrivastavel, R. and Upreti, R.K. (2004). Viral infections and trace elements; A complex interaction. *Current Sci*, 87: 1536 – 1554.

Devi, W. D., Bonysana, R., Singh, K. D., Koijam, A. S., Mukherjee, P. K. and

- Rajashekar, Y. (2024), Bio-economic potential of ethno-entomophagy and its therapeutics in India. NPJ Sci. Food, 8 p. 15.
- Dun, W; Yan-yu, B., Jiang-Hang, L. and Chuan-xi, Z, (2004): Nutritional value of the field cricket (*Gryllus Testaceus walker*). *Entomogica sinica*. Vol. 11, No 4 275 – 90.
- Eggleton, P. (2020). The State of the world's insects. Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour., 45 pp. 61-82.
- Giribet, G. and Edgecombe, G. D. (2019). "The Phylogeny and Evolutionary History of Arthropods." *Current Biology*, **29**(12), R592–R602
- Igwe, C. U, Onwuliri, V. A. Ojiako A. O. and Arukwe, U. (2011). Effects of *Macrotermes nigeriensis* base diet on hepatic and serum Lipids of albino rats. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied sciences* 5:906 – 910.
- Jose, O. Tchuinkam I; Waimane, A. Magard J. O. H. Niassy, S. and Meutchieye, F. (2022) *Lepidopterans* of economic importance in Cameroon: a systematic review *J. agr. Food Res.* 8 100286.
- Kipkoech, C., Jaster-Keller, J., Gottschalk, J., Wesonga, J. M. and Maul, R. (2023), African traditional use of edible insects and challenges towards the future trends of food and feed. *J. Insects Food Feed*, 9 (8) pp. 965-988
- Magara, H. J. O., Niassy, S., Ayieko, M. A., Mukundamago, M., Egunu, J. P., Tanga C. M., Kimathi, E. K., Ongere, J. O., Fiaboe, K. K. M. and Hugel, S. N (2021). Edible Crickets *Orthopetera* around the world distribution, Nutritional value and other benefits. A review. *Front. Nutr.* 7, 537915.
- Ojha, S. Bekhit, A. E., Grune, T. and Schluter, O. K. (2021). Bioavailability of nutrients from edible insects. *Current opinion in food science* 41, 1-9.

Okalebo, J. R., Gathua, K. W. and Woomer, P. L, (2002) laboratory methods of soil and plant analysis.

A working manual 2nd Edition Nairobi, Kenya; TSBF. Ciat and Cacted Africa, pp 155.

Oliveira, L. A., Pereira, S. M. S., Dias, K. A., Paes, S., Grancieri, M., Jimenez, L.

G. S., de Carvalho, C. W. P., de Oliveira, E. E., Martino, H. S. D. and Lucia, C. M. D. (2024).

Nutritional content, amino acid profile, and protein properties of edible insects (*Tenebrio molitor* and *Gryllus assimilis*) powders at different stages of development J. Food Compost. Anal. 125.

Omuse, H. E., Tonnang, Z. T., Yusuf, A. A., Machekano, H., Egonyu, J.,

P., Kimathi, E., Mohamed, S. F., Kassie, M., Subramanian, S., Onditi, J., Mwangi, S., Ekesi, S. and Niassy, S. (2024). The global atlas of edible insects: analysis of diversity and commonality contributing to food systems and sustainability. Sci. Rep., 14, p. 5045,

Raheem, O., Carrascosa, C., Oluwole, O.B., Nieuwland, M., Saraiva, A.,

Millan, R. and Rapso, A. (2019), Traditional consumption of and rearing edible insects in Africa, Asia and Europe Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr., 59 (140) pp. 2169-2188,

Roifes, S. R., Pinna, K. and Whitney E. (2009). Understanding normal and clinical nutrition. Eight Ed.

Wadsworth Cengage Learning: 383.

Roth, A. R. and Townsend C. E. (2003) Nutrition and diet therapy 8th Ed. Delmar Learning, Thomson

Learning inc. Canada. 132.

Rumpold, B. A. and Schlüter, O. K. (2013). Potential and challenges of insects as an

innovative source for food and feed production. Innov. Food Sci. Emerg. Technol., 17, pp. 1.

Saura – Calixto, F. Canellas, J. and Soler, L. (1983). Dietary fibre components of the nitrogen free

extracts of demand kernels J. Sci. Food Agric. 36; 1419 – 1422.

Van Itterbeeck, J. and Pelozuelo, L. (2022) How many edible insect species are there? A not so simple question. *Diversity*, 14, 143.

Verspoor, R. L., Soglo, M., Adeoti, R., Djouaka, R., Fristedt, R., Langton, M., Moriana, R. Osborne, M., Parr, C. L., Powell, K., Hurst, G. O. D. and Landberg, R. (2020). Mineral analysis reveals extreme manganese concentrations in wild harvested and commercially available edible termites. *Scientific reports*, 10(1), 6146.